

Cache Memory Organization

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Abstract

Computer memory is organized into a hierarchy. At the highest level are the processor registers, next comes one or more levels of cache, main memory, which is usually made out of a dynamic random-access memory (DRAM) and at last external memory composed of magnetic disks and tapes. All of these are considered internal to the computer system. Cache is small high speed memory usually Static RAM (SRAM) that contains the most recently accessed pieces of main memory. Cache memories are the high speed buffers which are interested between the processors and main memory to capture those portion of the contents of the main memory which are currently in use. Since cache memories are typically 5 -10 times faster than main memory they can reduce the effective memory access time if carefully designed and implemented. In this paper, we are going to discuss the architectural specification, cache mapping techniques, write policies, performance optimization in detail with case study of Pentium processors implementing cache.

Index Terms- SRAM, DRAM, DMA,MESI

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Introduction

Memory Hierarchy

A hierarchical memory system can be used to close up the speed difference. The innermost layer within the CPU is register files which is directly addressable by ALU. Cache memory can be used to serve the buffer between CPU and main memory. Cache can be divided into multiple levels as shown in fig.(b) in order to improve efficiency.

Fig 1 Memory Hierarchy

As one goes down the memory hierarchy, one finds decreasing cost/bit, increasing capacity, and slower access time. It would be nice to use only the fastest memory, but because that is the most expensive memory, we trade off access time and cost by using more of the slower memory. The trick is to organize the data and programs in memory so that the memory words needed are usually in the fastest memory.

Cache Organization

Cache is usually designed to be user-transparent therefore in order to locate an item in the cache it is necessary to have some functions which maps the main memory address into cache location. In general, it is likely that most future accesses to main memory by the processor will be to locations recently accesses. So the cache automatically retains a copy of some of the recently used words from the DRAM. If the cache is designed properly, then most of the time the processor will request memory words that are already in the cache

Cache Specification

Cache memory implementation depends on multiple aspects such as principle of locality of reference, operations of cache, design aspects and cache bandwidth.

Principle of locality of reference

Since code is generally executed sequentially, virtually all programs repeat sections of code and repeatedly access the same or nearby data. This characteristic is embodied in the Principle of Locality, which has been found empirically to be obeyed by most programs. It applies to both instruction references and data references, though it is more likely in instruction references. There are two aspects, firstly is *temporal locality* in which individual locality once referred are likely to be referenced again in near future. Secondly, *spatial locality* in which references including the next location is likely to be near the last reference. And lastly *Sequential locality* which describes sequential location being referenced.

Cache Memory Organization

There are basically four placement policies which are named as direct, fully associative, set associative and sector mapping. Fully-Associative Mapping The first cache organization to be discussed is *fully-Associative cache*. Figure 2-5 shows a diagram of a Fully Associative cache. This organizational scheme allows any line in main memory to be stored at any location in the cache. Fully-Associative cache does not use cache pages, only lines. Main memory and cache memory are both divided into lines of equal size.

Fig 3 Fully Associative Mapping

For example Figure 2-5 shows that Line 1 of main memory is stored in Line 0 of cache. However this is not the only possibility, Line 1 could have been stored anywhere within the cache. Any cache line may store any memory line, hence the name, Fully Associative.

Direct mapping

Direct Mapped cache is also referred to as 1-Way set associative cache. In this scheme, main memory is divided into cache pages. The size of each page is equal to the size of the cache. Unlike the fully associative cache, the direct map cache may only store a specific line of memory within the same line of cache. For example, Line 0 of any page in memory must be stored in Line 0 of cache memory. Therefore if Line 0 of Page 0 is stored within the cache and Line 0 of page 1 is requested, then Line 0 of Page 0 will be replaced with Line 0 of Page 1.

Figure 4 shows a diagram of a direct map scheme. This scheme directly maps a memory line into an equivalent cache line, hence the name Direct Mapped cache.

Fig 4 Direct Mapping

Set Associative Mapping

A *Set-Associative* cache scheme is a combination of Fully-Associative and Direct Mapped caching schemes. A set-associate scheme works by dividing the cache SRAM into equal sections called cache ways. The cache page size is equal to the size of the cache way. Each cache way is treated like a small direct mapped cache.

Fig 5 Set Associative Mapping

To make the explanation clearer, let's look at a specific example. In this scheme, two lines of memory may be stored at any time. This scheme is less complex than a Fully-Associative cache because the number of comparators is equal to the number of cache ways.

Sector Mapping

In *sector mapping*, the main memory and the cache are both divided into sectors; each sector is composed of a number of blocks. Any sector in the main memory can map into any sector in the cache and a tag is stored with each sector in the cache to identify the main memory sector address. However, a complete sector is not transferred to the cache or back to the main memory as one unit. Instead, individual blocks are transferred as required. On cache sector miss, the required block of the sector is transferred into a specific location within one sector. The sector location in the cache is selected and all the other existing blocks in the sector in the cache are from a previous sector.

Cache Performance

The performance of a cache can be quantified in terms of the hit and miss rates, the cost of a hit, and the miss penalty, where a cache hit is a memory access that finds data in the cache and a cache miss is one that does not. When reading, the cost of a cache hit is roughly the time to access an entry in the cache. The miss penalty is the additional cost of replacing a cache line with one containing the desired data.

$$\text{Access Time} = h\text{Cost} * (m\text{Rate} + m\text{Penalty})$$

Where,

hCost - Hit cost or fastest memory access time

mRate - Miss Rate

mPenalty- Slow memory access time

Since the speeds of the actual memory used will be improving "independently", most effort in cache design is spent on fast control and decreasing the miss rates. We can classify misses into three categories, compulsory misses, capacity misses and conflict misses. Compulsory misses are when data is loaded into the cache for the first time and are unavoidable. Capacity misses are when data is reloaded because the cache is not large enough to hold all the data no matter how we organize the data (i.e. even if we changed the hash function and made it omniscient). All other misses are conflict misses - there is theoretically enough space in the cache to avoid the miss but our fast hash function caused a miss anyway.

Write Policies

A write policy determines how the cache deals with a write cycle. The two common write policies are **Write-Back** and **Write-Through**.

In **Write-Back policy**, the cache acts like a buffer. That is, when the processor starts a write cycle the cache receives the data and terminates the cycle. The cache then writes the data back to main memory when the system bus is available. This method provides the greatest performance by allowing the processor to continue its tasks while main memory is updated at a later time. However, controlling writes to main memory increase the cache's complexity and cost.

The second method is the **Write-Through policy**. As the name implies, the processor writes through the cache to main memory. The cache may update its contents, however the write cycle does not end until the data is stored into main memory. This

method is less complex and therefore less expensive to implement. The performance with a Write-Through policy is lower since the processor must wait for main memory to accept the data.

Cache Coherence Protocols

Fig 7 Cache Coherence Problem

Figure 7 depicts an example of the cache coherence problem. Memory initially contains the value 0 for location x , and processors 0 and 1 both read location x into their caches. If processor 0 writes location x in its cache with the value 1, then processor 1's cache now contains the stale value 0 for location x . Subsequent reads of location x by processor 1 will continue to return the stale, cached value of 0. This is likely not what the programmer expected when she/he wrote the program. The expected behavior is for a read by any processor to return the most up-to-date copy of the datum. This is exactly what a cache coherence protocol does: it ensures that requests for a certain datum always return the most recent value

The coherence protocol achieves this goal by taking action whenever a location is written. More precisely, since the granularity of a cache coherence protocol is a cache line, the protocol takes action whenever any cache line is written. Protocols can take two kinds of actions when a cache line L is written, they may either *invalidate* all copies of L from the other caches in the machine, or they may *update* those lines with the new value being written.

Case Study – Pentium (R) Processor

This section examines internal cache on the Pentium(R) processor. The purpose of this section is to describe the cache scheme that the Pentium(R) processor uses and to provide an overview of how the Pentium(R) processor maintains cache consistency within a system. Pentium(R) processor cache is implemented differently than the systems shown in the previous examples. The first difference is the cache system is internal to the processor, i.e. integrated into the part. Therefore, no external hardware is needed to take advantage of this cache helping to reduce the overall cost of the system. Another advantage is the speed of memory request responses. For example, a 100MHz Pentium(R) processor has an external bus speed of 66MHz. All external cache must operate at a maximum speed of 66mhz. However, an internal cache operates at 100MHz. Not only does the internal cache respond faster, it also has a wider data interface. An external interface is only 64-bits wide while the internal interface between the cache and processor prefetch buffer is 256-bits wide. Therefore, a huge increase in performance is possible by integrating the cache into the CPU.

A third difference is that the cache is divided into two separate pieces to improve performance a data cache and a code cache, each at 8K. This division allows both code and data to readily cross page boundaries without having to overwrite one another.

Fig 8 Pentium Processor Cache

The cache subsystem can be divided into three functional blocks: SRAM, Tag RAM, and the Cache Controller. In actual designs, these blocks may be implemented by multiple chips or all may be combined into a single chip. Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) is the memory block which holds the data. The size of the SRAM determines the size of the cache. The cache controller is the brains behind the cache. Its responsibilities include: performing the snoops and snarfs, updating the SRAM and TRAM and implementing the write policy. The cache controller is also responsible for determining if memory request is cacheable² and if a request is a cache hit or miss.

Cache Consistency in Pentium

The Pentium(R) processor maintains cache consistency with the MESI⁵ protocol. MESI is used to allow the cache to decide if a memory entry should be updated or invalidated. With the Pentium(R) processor, two functions are performed to allow its internal cache to stay consistent, Snoop Cycles and Cache Flushing. The Pentium(R) processor snoops during memory transactions on the system bus⁶. That is, when another bus master performs a write, the Pentium(R) processor snoops the address. If the Pentium(R) processor contains the data, the processor will schedule a write-back. Cache flushing is the mechanism by which the Pentium(R) processor clears its cache. A cache flush may result from actions in either hardware or software. During a cache flush, the Pentium(R) processor writes back all modified data. It then invalidates its cache. After the Pentium(R) processor finishes its write-backs, it then generates a special bus cycle called the Flush Acknowledge Cycle. This signal allows lower level caches, to flush their contents as well.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have discussed the memory hierarchies, cache memory organization and their design aspects with performance. However, you can see the details in the Pentium(R) Processors implementation cross several of the initially defined boundaries. It is important to understand that the Pentium(R) Processor uses only one method to implement cache. There are many other valid way to do the same things, but, they all lead to the same place. Cache is simply a high speed piece of memory that stores a snapshot of main memory which enables the processor higher performance.

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